

Evaluation of Aspartate Aminotransferase to-Platelet Ratio Index as a Non-Invasive Marker for Liver Cirrhosis

INTRODUCTION

Cirrhosis has now emerged as an important public health problem globally. Cirrhosis is currently the leading cause of death among liver-related diseases. It is characterized by defective microcirculation, liver parenchymal and anatomical defects, change in hepatic architecture, distortion, and regenerative nodular formation, which finally result in progressive fibrosis. It is one of the top fifteen causes of death globally. It is commonly seen in developed countries leading to considerable mortality and morbidity. When it has reached its final stages of progression, it becomes irreversible and the only treatment often left after that would be liver transplantation, while in its earlier stages, management is focused to reduce the progression through specific treatment modalities and drugs targeting the etiology, thereby halting the fibrosis. (1)

Alcohol liver disease is the final stage of liver cell pathology, which impacts the development of nodules and decreased liver function (1). A liver diagnostic test currently offers the most reliable general analysis of liver necrosis, inflammatory activity, and pathology for the prognosis of liver disease. This may be a result of interobserver variability and biopsy sampling error; the length and segmentation of the diagnostic test affect its validity and histopathology results. The use of liver biopsy is limited by several alternative issues, including trauma, aberrant conditions, and bleeding (2).

Aspartate aminotransferase to platelet ratio index (APRI) and fibro test scoring methods make use of biochemical markers that don't directly correlate with fibrosis and use a statistical approach to forecast the stage of fibrosis. A variety of hepatic imaging methods have also shown promise in the evaluation and treatment of liver fibrosis. However, techniques including transient elastography (4), fibroscan (5), and fibrocheck (3) have lately come into use (5-7). However, diffusion MR imaging and perfusion MR imaging are utilized to diagnose advanced fibrosis. APRI is an extremely effective non-invasive diagnosis for progressive liver fibrosis.

There have been very few non-invasive investigations undertaken worldwide to determine the degree and prognosis of liver fibrosis in cirrhotic people. APRI, or aspartate aminotransferase: thrombocyte magnitude relation Index, is recommended as a specific indicator for cirrhosis prognostication (8,9). Patients with cirrhosis have a cost-effective alternative to liver biopsy and other non-invasive procedures in the form of APRI, which has been quickly evaluated in foreign countries (10,11) and a few Indian populations (12). However, the Asian community does not receive many of these. Liver biopsies are the gold standard approach for assessing liver fibrosis, but because they are invasive, they can cause significant problems.

Wai et al. developed a novel "AST to platelet ratio indicator" (APRI). APRI greater than 1.5 has the area under the receiver's operating curve (AUROC) values of 80 and 89 percent for advanced fibrosis F3-F4 and cirrhosis, respectively. (13). The APRI score is linked to alcoholic liver disease, hepatitis C virus infection, human immunodeficiency virus infection, and co-HCV infection. Numerous studies have found a link between APRI and the viruses described above. (14,15.) APRI is also good for people who have NAFLD. According to Angelo et al.'s retrospective study (n=320), the APRI showed an 80% accuracy rate for

predicting liver-related poor outcomes in NAFLD patients and a 63% accuracy rate for predicting mortality or liver transplantation. (16).

So, in light of the information we now have, we have the predisposition to pass judgment. APRI was evaluated for its sensitivity and specificity as a diagnostic tool by several studies, and it was found to be the best non-invasive diagnostic tool for liver disease in a sample of the Indian population. The World Health Organization (WHO) published a global status report on alcohol and health for India in 2018 that found that 30% of adults in that country consume alcohol, with spirits being the most popular type (93%) while beer and wine make up 7% and 1%, respectively. Four 12-ounce cans of beer, 15 ounces of wine, or four 4-ounce glasses of whiskey used every day for 10 year² have a 10-15% chance of developing cirrhosis. (17-19)

When drinking wine as opposed to spirits or beer, the prevalence of cirrhosis is significantly lower. Alcohol is noted as being responsible for more than 40% of liver fatalities, per the WHO database. Cirrhosis consequences include ascites, coagulation problems, hepatorenal syndrome, varices, hepatopulmonary hypertension, hepatic encephalopathy, spontaneous bacterial peritonitis, and hepatocellular malignancy. These problems are caused by either abnormal synthetic function, portal hypertension, or both. Liver fibrosis is associated with chronic liver damage caused by multiple sources at the same time.

Aim:

To evaluate the effectiveness of the Aspartate aminotransferase-to-platelet ratio index (APRI) as a non-invasive prognostic marker for liver cirrhosis.

Objective :

- ☐ To correlate APRI with various etiologies of cirrhosis
- ☐ To correlate APRI with the severity of cirrhosis by MELD and child-pugh score

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

History:

The term "cirrhosis" is thought to have originated from the Greek text "Kirrhos," which describes the tan color that develops in the liver as the disease progresses. When early researchers saw that persons with advanced liver illness with jaundice had altered mental status, they began to investigate the connection between liver disease & cerebral dysfunction. The changes in the mental state of those with liver illness were first discovered and characterized by Freirch, also referred to be the Father of Modern Hepatology, as early as the 1940s. (20) It was later discovered through research that these patients had an elevated prescription for ammonia and shunned foods like meat and eggs. The other treatment option was afterward saline, laxatives, enemas, a high-carbohydrate diet, and lactulose.

GROSS ANATOMY:

The liver is located in the abdominal cavity, beneath the diaphragm, in the right hypochondriac and epigastric areas. An adult liver typically weighs between 1400 and 1600 gm. The falciform ligament separates the liver into its right and left lobes. The caudate and quadrate lobes, which are located inferiorly and superiorly, respectively, separate the right lobe into two further smaller lobes. The liver is further separated into eight functioning segments with its own biliary and circulatory systems, allowing for the maintenance of relative hemostasis during resection. Hepatic and portal veins both give blood to the liver. The portal vein supplies the liver with about 80% of its blood, which is not very well oxygenated. The hepatic artery, which is adequately oxygenated, delivers the remaining 20%. The Glisson's capsule, a thin layer of connective tissue covering the liver, contains mast cells,

fibroblasts, type I collagen fibers that are uniformly arranged, type III collagen fibers that are distributed throughout, & sensory nerves. (23)

Definition:

"The process through which liver parenchyma turns into a fibrosed state and then progresses to nodule formation" is the definition of cirrhosis. Cirrhosis results from this fibrotic chronic liver disease. Cirrhosis may be caused by a variety of factors. Cirrhosis is not present in cases when nodular development is present; instead, this condition is known as nodular regenerative hyperplasia. (24)

Epidemiology of Cirrhosis:

Geographical location and the underlying etiology have a significant impact on the occurrence of cirrhosis. The most frequent cause of chronic hepatitis—which accounts for 20 to 30 percent of cases during twenty years—is hepatitis C. Hepatitis C infection affects an estimated 170 million people worldwide. Progressive liver disorders brought on by Hep C are frequently associated with the development of nodules, portal fibrosis, and bridging fibrosis. The liver is typically tiny and shrunken in macronodular cirrhosis. (25)

Similar findings to those of Hepatitis B are also seen, but fewer people go on to develop cirrhosis (5 percent -20 percent) Patients who test positive may have either infectivity or hepatitis B core (HBc) and surface (HBs) antigen (HBe). Every year, some 30 million people get Hep B infections, with nearly 20% progressing to the cirrhotic stage. (26)

Aetiology of Cirrhosis:

Cirrhosis incidence is rising globally as a result of several factors. Due to a rise in risk factors like obesity, drunkenness, and smoking, developed countries have seen an especially noticeable trend. Thus, many liver disease pathologies, including hepatitis, and alcoholic and non-alcoholic steatohepatitis, are to blame for this recent rise. The most prominent causes of cirrhosis in developing nations continue to be hepatitis B and C. Tyrosinemia, type IV glycogenesis, primary biliary cirrhosis, primary sclerosing cholangitis, autoimmune hepatitis, Budd-Chiari syndrome, galactosemia, iron overload (as in Wilson's disease), primary biliary cirrhosis, Budd-Chiari syndrome, and other conditions affecting venous outflow like Budd-Chiari syndrome are additional (27)

PHYSIOLOGICAL FUNCTIONS OF LIVER

The liver is essential to every organ system in the body. By interacting with the digestive and endocrine systems, it promotes digestion and metabolism. In addition to managing cholesterol homeostasis, it facilitates the storage of iron, copper, and fat-soluble vitamins. It contributes to protein synthesis and clotting factors in hematology. The liver converts heme into conjugated and unconjugated bilirubin. It makes carrier proteins and is crucial for the metabolism of sex hormones. In the immune system, Kupffer cells and Pit cells are crucial. (28)

Pathophysiology of Cirrhosis of the liver:

The primary method for diagnosing cirrhosis of the liver is histology, which involves examining the liver parenchyma macroscopically as well as the histological alterations in the liver cells. Additionally, the histology of the underlying condition, which in some cases can be fatal, such as HE, matches the clinical indications of liver cirrhosis. The key pathological

finding in the liver's histological analysis is the presence of fibroid tissue with scarring, regenerating nodules with diminished hepatocellular mass, and splanchnic system blood flow changes as a result. (29,30)

The key indicator of worsening liver damage is liver fibrosis. The functional unit of the liver is the lobule, which is made up of hepatocytes arranged in branching plates surrounding a central vein connecting to the portal tract. Bile ductules, a venule branch of the portal vein, and an arteriole branch of the hepatic artery comprise the portal tract. Blood enters the lobule via sinusoids between the hepatocytes plates via the portal vein and hepatic artery branches. The Disse space, which is made up of hepatic stellate cells and filled with blood plasma, separates the hepatocytes from the sinusoids (HSC). Fenestrated endothelia are lying on a connective tissue sheet on one side. On the other hand, hepatocytes can absorb proteins and other components of plasma thanks to microvilli that extend into the Disse gap. Toxins or other stimuli cause HSC to become activated and to multiply. In the Disse area, they phenotypically transform into myofibroblast-like cells that produce an extracellular matrix. Hepatic microvilli destruction and the loss of endothelial fenestrations (sinusoidal capillarization) lead to reduced nutrition absorption by hepatocytes. The build-up of the matrix causes the liver parenchyma's structural deformation and resistance to sinusoidal blood flow. Portal hypertension has this as its foundation. (31)

It is crucial to remember that liver fibrosis is dynamic, with matrix buildup occurring alongside matrix breakdown and remodeling, with the process leaning more one way or the other. Remodeling and, to some extent, regression is still possible once cirrhosis has developed. Age and gender are just two of the many elements that control this balance. Additionally, there is a genetic component, and research into liver fibrosis may eventually center on finding genes that are dysregulated in the liver. In chapter six, it is covered how

genes control how estrogens affect liver fibrosis. In addition to fibrosis, the course of chronic liver disease includes neo-angiogenesis & chronic inflammation. (32)

Clinical features of Cirrhosis:

Nearly half of cirrhosis patients typically have no symptoms and only experience symptoms in the later stages of the disease. Patients experience non-specific symptoms in the early stages, such as anorexia and weight loss, and occasionally generalized malaise and weakness. They experience distinct difficulties later on in the disease, such as upper GI hemorrhage and hepatic encephalopathy. (33)

The presentation differs depending on the patient's stage of illness as well. The most typical symptoms of an advanced disease are jaundice and hepatic encephalopathy, either with or without coagulopathy. Jaundice is almost often linked to extremely itchy skin.

Additionally, it should be emphasized that after liver donation, this acute pruritis frequently develops on its own and is treatment-resistant.

Splenomegaly, engorged veins, and ascites are additional clinical characteristics that are frequently encountered alongside cirrhosis. Additionally, it should be emphasized that people with cirrhosis have a higher frequency of *Helicobacter pylori* infections. Upper GI bleeding is twice as common in people with ulcer disease who have cirrhosis. Long-term ascitis patients also experience umbilical hernia during the course of the condition; surgical intervention is only considered when the hernia interferes with the patient's daily activities. Patients with cirrhosis are more likely to develop gallstones, particularly pigment stones, and those who develop cirrhosis after developing the alcohol-related liver disease are more likely to develop pancreatitis, pancreatic calcification, and enlargement of the parotid gland. (34)

Patients with persistent cirrhosis often have foul breath that smells like feces. It may also occasionally be regarded as a well-known indicator of hepatic coma.

In accordance with the investigation profile, we discover leukopenia and hypoalbuminemia in patients who also have chronic cirrhosis and malnutrition.

Additionally, some patients exhibit Dupuytren's contractures, which frequently originate from the palmar fascia thickening. Clubbing is another typical cirrhosis patient symptom.

The majority of skin lesions are spider nevi, which are primarily seen along the route of the superior vena cava. Given that cirrhosis is frequently encountered in both pregnant women and children, it might not be a diagnostic criterion for cirrhosis.

Pathophysiology of Clinical features of Cirrhosis:

The main pathophysiology behind the clinical features of cirrhosis among chronic liver disease patients lies due to vasodilation and subsequent hyperdynamic circulation following it, resulting in increased peripheral and portal blood flow. This is alongside increased cardiac output and tachycardia with prominent precordial impulses and an ejection systolic murmur. Decreased vasomotor tone results in decreased vasoconstriction during Valsalva. It is noted that autonomic dysfunction is often seen in advanced cases with poor prognosis. Activation of the RAS & sympathetic system results in sodium & water retention causing ascites and a volume-overloaded state. This is further worsened by other mediators of inflammation such as angiotensin, cytokines, nitric oxide, and endothelial and vascular growth factors. Increased nitric oxide results in splanchnic vasodilation and increased portal venous pressure and increased intrahepatic pressure resulting in clinical features. (35)

SYMPTOMS OF LIVER CIRRHOSIS

- General malaise, fatigue
- Anorexia/weight loss
- A feeling of an enlarged abdomen
- Swollen abdomen/legs
- Nose bleed / bleeding from lower limbs
- Jaundice/itch
- Hand tremors

Physical findings

- Skin pigmentation
- Xanthoma
- Spider angioma
- Palmar erythema
- Finger clubbing
- Caput medusa
- Gynecomastia
- Fever
- Hepatic halitosis
- Jaundice
- Ascites
- Asterix
- Bleeding plaque

Complications of Cirrhosis:

Major complications of cirrhosis include:

- i. Portal hypertension
 - a. Esophageal varices
 - b. Portal hypertension-associated gastropathy
 - c. Spontaneous bacterial peritonitis
 - d. Splenomegaly
 - e. Ascites
- ii. Type I and II hepatorenal syndrome
- iii. Hepatopulmonary syndrome
- iv. Pulmonary hypertension
- v. Malnutrition
- vi. Bone-associated disorders like osteopenia and osteoporosis
- vii. Coagulopathy
- viii. Hematological abnormalities like anemia and hemolysis (36)

Prognosis:

Important factors that determine the prognosis of ascites cases include an increase in ascites, change in prothrombin time and its prolongation, upper GI bleeding, increase in intake of alcohol, increase in serum bilirubin levels, increase of serum alkaline phosphatase, reduction in the serum albumin. Several scoring systems help us in determining the prognosis of cirrhosis patients and the need for liver transplantation. The most common among them are Child pugh classification & MELD. (37)

Child-Pugh classification:

This classification mainly focuses on the short-term prognosis of individuals. It has 3 classes namely A, B, and C. The classification takes into account of the following parameters:

1. Jaundice
2. Hepatic encephalopathy
3. Ascites
4. Prothrombin time
5. Serum albumin

Thus the final scoring pattern for this classification holds as A – 5 to 6, B – 7 to 9, and C is 10-15. (38)

FACTORS	UNITS	1	2	3
Serum bilirubin	mol/L	<34	34-51	>51
	mg/dL	<2.0	2.0-3.0	>3.0
Serum albumin	g/L	>35	30-35	<30
	g/dL	>3.5	3.0-3.5	<3.0
Prothrombin time	Seconds	0-4	4-6	>6
INR		<1.7	1.7-2.3	>2.3
Ascites		None	Slight	Moderate
Hepatic encephalopathy		None	Minimal	Advanced
INR= International Normalized ratio Child-Pugh class can be: - Class A= score 5-6 Class B= score 7-9 Class C= score of 10 or above				

Table 1: Child pug scoring system

MELD:

It means the Model for End-stage liver disease (MELD) is used primarily for the prognosis of CLD patients who go in for a TIPS procedure. It includes the factors such as serum prothrombin, creatinine, and serum bilirubin. A few studies have also stated that this scoring system can be utilized for the prediction of waiting list (liver transplantation) mortality among patients, thus is now widely used for the same purpose.

The 3-month survival and prediction of the MELD score are explained in the following study by Aiello et al. (39) Table 2.

MELD= 3.78 x log_e [bilirubin (mg/dL)] ± 11.2 x log_e [INR] ± 9.57 x log_e [Creatinine (mg/dL)] + 6.43	
The 3-month survival for each MELD score	
3-month mortality, %	MELD score
1.9 – 3.7	<9
6 – 20	10 – 19
19.6 – 45.5	20 – 29
52.6 – 74.5	30 – 39
71 – 100	>40
MELD, a model for end-stage liver disease	

Table 2: MELD score

Hepatic Encephalopathy:

There are three types of HE depending on the nature of association with liver disease, they are:

Type A: Encephalopathy associated with acute liver failure

Type B: Encephalopathy with portal-systemic bypass & no overt liver disease

Type C: Encephalopathy commonly associated with cirrhosis & portal hypertension

Another very important parameter utilized now recently to grade patients with Hepatic encephalopathy is the West Heaven score. (40)

Spontaneous bacterial peritonitis (SBP):

In the absence of a malignancy or an intraabdominal cause of infection that may be surgically treated, spontaneous bacterial peritonitis (SBP) is defined as a positive ascitic fluid culture and a polymorphonuclear leucocyte (PMN) count in ascitic fluid of less than 250/cu.mm¹. To distinguish this infection from surgical peritonitis, Correia and Conn came up with the name "spontaneous bacterial peritonitis" in 1975. (41)

Patients with chronic liver disease who have hydrothorax may develop spontaneous bacterial empyema (SBE). A polymorphonuclear leucocyte (PMN) count of less than 250/cu.mm in pleural fluid and a positive pleural fluid culture, or a fluid PMN count of less than 500/cu.mm in the absence of growth in pleural fluid culture, can be used to describe it. When pneumonia is not present, this diagnosis is given. (42)

NONINVASIVE SERUM MARKERS

Types

Serum indicators for the liver can either be specific or nonspecific. They could either be indirect indicators of hepatic dysfunction or direct indicators of the fibrosis process (such as glycoproteins and collagens) (e.g., prothrombin time, platelet count, and albumin). Some serum marker panels are proprietary (e.g., FibroTest or the enhanced liver fibrosis [ELF] score); others combine frequently obtained laboratory tests (e.g., AST/APRI), patient characteristics (e.g., FIB-4, nonalcoholic fatty liver disease fibrosis score, or BARD score), or are the results of the multivariable analysis.

Diagnosis

The majority of indicators correctly classify individuals as having cirrhosis or normal liver parenchyma, however, they incorrectly distinguish between intermediate stages of fibrosis. In studies on the hepatitis C virus (HCV), the area under the receiver operating characteristic (AUROC) for the diagnosis of cirrhosis at the respective cutoff was 0.84 (APRI) versus 0.86 (FibroTest), 0.86 (APRI) versus 0.87 (Forns index), 0.89 (APRI) versus 0.88 (platelet count), and 0.86 (APRI) versus 0.84. (FIB-4).¹ In a different multicenter research, the inclusion of FibroTest to APRI reduced the number of biopsies needed for the diagnosis of cirrhosis from 71 percent to 53.5 percent. (43)

Limitations

Serum indicators can be produced in an outpatient context, are easily repeatable, noninvasive, and applicable to large populations. The inability to distinguish between intermediate phases of fibrosis is one of the limitations, along with generalizability, cost of proprietary tests,

overestimation in some situations (such as increased bilirubin in Gilbert's syndrome or hemolysis), and overestimation in general. (44)

$$\text{APRI} = \frac{\text{AST (Upper limit of Normal)}}{\text{Platelet Count (10}^9\text{/L)}} \times 100$$

Example 1:-

A 61- year old patient with chronic HCV infection, and blood analysis showing AST 120 U/L (ULN or upper limit of normal =40 U/L) and a platelet count of 50 K/uL.

$$\text{APRI} = \frac{\text{AST/AST (ULN)} \times 100}{\text{platelet}}$$
$$\frac{120/40 \times 100}{50} = 6$$

This would suggest the presence of advanced fibrosis or cirrhosis.

ELASTOGRAPHY

Types

The intrinsic stiffness of the liver parenchyma, as measured by elastography, is correlated with the presence of advanced fibrosis. Techniques based on elastography may use either magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) or ultrasound (US). Either mechanical excitation of tissue by physical compression, use of an acoustic radiation force impulse, or controlled external vibration is required for elastography (strain or shear wave). Shear wave elastography tracks how shear waves move through tissues. (45)

Stiffer tissue allows shear waves to spread more quickly. A few popular methods are magnetic resonance elastography, vibration-controlled transient elastography (VCTE), and two-dimensional shear-wave elastography (2D SWE) (MRE). Results from US-based methods are frequently presented in kilopascals, with values of roughly 5 kPa or less suggesting a normal liver and larger than 12 to 14 kPa implying cirrhosis. Results from MRE are around one-third of those from transient elastography; levels below 2.9 kPa indicate a normal liver, while those above 5.2 kPa indicate the existence of cirrhosis. (45)

Diagnosis

Compared to detecting severe fibrosis, all diagnostic techniques perform better in detecting cirrhosis (stage 2 or higher). At a threshold of 14.5 kPa, VCTE showed an 89 percent specificity for cirrhosis and an 83 percent sensitivity when compared to liver biopsy. 4,5 A threshold greater than 3.63 kPa (AUROC 0.92) demonstrated 86 percent sensitivity and 91 percent specificity for differentiating advanced fibrosis from stage 0 to 2 fibrosis among nonalcoholic fatty liver disease patients receiving MRE. 6 VCTE and 2D SWE displayed comparable performance traits for cirrhosis diagnosis (AUROCs were 0.98 and 0.96). Studies contrasting the MRE and VCTE have produced inconsistent results regarding whether a test is better, particularly during intermediate stages. MRE has better completion rates (8,9) (94 percent versus 84 percent) (46)

Limitations

Absolute liver stiffness readings have a poor correlation with intermediate stages of fibrosis.

The prevalence of incomplete exams and unreliable exams vary by approach, especially in patients who are obese. Liver stiffness may be overestimated by acute inflammation, cholestasis, nonfasting condition, increased arterial pressure, and hepatic congestion.

Compared to serum indicators, radiological markers have higher diagnostic accuracy. (47) A significant change from baseline in liver stiffness or a serum marker may be used as a prognostic tool to identify patients who are most likely to progress over time.

NON-INVASIVE CLINICAL SCORING SYSTEM in NAFLD:

FIBROSURE (FibroTest), Fibrometer, NAFLD fibrosis score, BARD, European Liver Fibrosis Score (ELF), Fib-4, AST-to-platelet ratio index (APRI), and AST/ALT ratio are the main clinical scoring systems explored in NAFLD. The comparison of these tests' accuracy in terms of their positive and negative predictive values revealed that less expensive and more straightforward laboratory tests (such as APRI and AST/ALT ratio) are similar to more sophisticated and expensive tests (such as TIMP-1, FibroSURE, and ELF). The accuracy of these tests in identifying either absent or advanced fibrosis is high. (48)

APRI (aspartate aminotransferase platelet ratio index)

The formula is used to determine the APRI value. A score of 40 is the upper limit of normal.

- <0.5 rules out significant fibrosis
- >1.5 rules in significant fibrosis
- > 2 cirrhosis

For individuals with chronic hepatitis B and C, the aspartate aminotransferase to platelet ratio index (APRI) has been recommended as a noninvasive test for diagnosing hepatic fibrosis. In patients with chronic hepatitis C virus infection or alcoholic liver disease, APRI has also been used to forecast mortality due to liver-related causes. APRI has been extensively researched in NAFLD, and as its values tend to rise as fibrosis progresses, it may be able to predict fibrosis in NAFLD. (49)

Material And Method:

Study design:

Case control Study

Study Setting

The study was conducted in the Department of Medicine, at Datta Meghe Institute of Higher Education and Research, a tertiary care teaching hospital situated in the rural area of Wardha District. The study was undertaken after approval from the institute's ethical committee.

Ethics committee approval:

The study received clearance from the institutional ethical committee of DMIHER, Sawangi (M), Wardha after submitting a synopsis mentioning all the proposed study designs and study protocols. The corresponding approval letter numbered DMIMS (DU)/IEC/2022/1230 is attached here in annexure I

Duration of study:

December 2020 to November 2022

Study participants:

All the patients > 17 years of age regardless of gender or ethnicity who undergo ultrasonography at AVBRH, Sawangi were selected after written informed consent was obtained from all participants.

Sample size:

$$\text{Sample Size: } \frac{Z\alpha^2 * (p)*(1-p)}{c^2}$$

Where:

Z= Z value (1.96 for 95% confidence level)

P= percentage of picking a choice expressed as a decimal

This was found to be 80% for the present study which was expressed as 0.80

C= confidence interval expressed as a decimal

So, the sample size was calculated as per the formula

$$= \frac{(1.96)^2 \times 0.8 \times 0.2}{(0.05)^2}$$

Where:

Reference Study: Sample Size =200

Cases = 100 (with cirrhosis)

Controls = 100 (healthy without cirrhosis)

SELECTION CRITERIA FOR SUBJECTS UNDER STUDY

INCLUSION CRITERIA

- People with HbsAg/HCV positive status
- People with *alcoholic liver disease (ALD)
- Age: 18-70 years, and
- Either gender.

EXCLUSION CRITERIA

- Obese patients
- Patients with hepatocellular carcinoma,
- Patients on invasive mechanical ventilation, and
- Patients with congestive cardiac failure
- Patient on antiplatelet and patient with febrile illness affecting platelets

FLOW CHART FOR PLAN OF STUDY

METHODS:

- All the patients revealing the history and physical examination suggestive of cirrhosis of the liver were screened for enrolment in the study. All routine investigations including complete blood count, liver function tests, kidney function tests, and prothrombin time with INR were done on admission. Ultrasonography of the abdomen was done.
- Cirrhosis of the Liver was diagnosed on basis of clinical examination, laboratory findings, and ultrasonography findings.
- Now at this point, patients were enrolled in the study after applying exclusion criteria.
- Child pug score and MELD score on admission were calculated by using various variables used in the scoring system as shown in **Table 1** and **Table 2**, respectively, and were correlated with APRI. Patient outcome was considered in terms of Discharge, Death, and Length of hospital stay and was correlated with APRI. Patients' APRI was correlated with the Child pug score and MELD score.

Complete Blood count parameters:

Haemoglobin (g/dL), total leucocyte count (per μL), and platelet count (per μL) were measured after taking samples with appropriate aseptic measures. The sample was taken in an EDTA bulb (dipotassium Ethylenediamine-tetra-acetic acid) and measured within an hour when maintained at room temperature. Horiba- Pentra XLR was used for this purpose.

Liver function test, Serum creatinine, Serum sodium, Serum potassium:

The blood samples were collected from the patients under all aseptic precautions in a plain bulb and were centrifuged, and the serum was separated. All the parameters including total bilirubin (mg/dL), serum albumin (g/dL), SGPT (U/L), SGOT (U/L), serum creatinine (mg/dL), serum sodium (mmol/L), and serum potassium(mg/dl) were analyzed and estimated by VITROS 5600 by turbidimetry.

Coagulation profile:

The blood samples were collected from the patients under all aseptic precautions in a sodium citrate bulb and Prothrombin time (seconds) and INR were analyzed with an Acute care diagnostics machine.

Table 3: - Reference values of variables (All the reference values are according to Central clinical research laboratory, AVBRH rural hospital, Sawangi (M), Wardha)

Variables	Reference range
Hemoglobin	12 – 17 g/dL
WBC count	4000 – 11000 per μ L
Platelet count	150000 – 450000 per μ L
Serum Potassium	3.6-5.2mg/dL
Serum creatinine	0.5 – 1.3 mg/dL
Serum sodium	135 – 145 mmol/L
Total bilirubin	0.2 – 1.5 mg/dL
Serum albumin	3.5 – 4.5 g/dL
SGPT & SGOT (U/L)	10 – 40 U/L
Prothrombin time(seconds)	9 – 11 seconds

Statistical Analysis

Statistical Analysis was performed with help of Epi Info (TM) 7.2.2.2 EPI INFO is a trademark of the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC).

Descriptive statistical analysis was performed to calculate the means with corresponding standard deviations (s.d.). A test of proportion was used to find the Standard Normal Deviate (Z) to compare the different proportions and Chi-square (χ^2) test was performed to find the associations. t-test was used to compare the means of the two groups. ROC (receiver operating characteristic curve) was used to find the under curve (AUC) followed by Youden Method was used cut-off value of different parameters for outcomes. Diagnostic accuracy, sensitivity, specificity, Positive Predictive Value (PPV), and Negative Predictive Value (NPV) were calculated to find the efficacy of diagnostic tools. $p < 0.05$ was taken to be statistically significant.

Analysis of the patients with liver cirrhosis:

Table 4: Comparison of baseline characteristics and laboratory parameters among cases and controls

Parameters	Group	Mean	s.d.	t-value	p-value
Baseline characteristics					
Age	Case	42.85	13.73	5.08	<0.0001 S
	Control	52.89	14.24		
Laboratory parameters					
HB	Case	9.85	3.28	0.44	0.66 NS
	Control	10.03	2.63		
WBC count	Case	9793.90	8279.75	0.39	0.70 NS
	Control	9363.90	7140.26		
PLC	Case	1.29	1.01	3.32	<0.0001
	Control	1.76	1.01		
APTT	Case	37.58	8.05	4.08	<0.0001 S
	Control	31.14	13.55		
PT	Case	20.72	6.22	0.56	0.57 NS
	Control	20.20	6.79		
INR	Case	1.67	0.53	1.49	0.14 NS
	Control	1.57	0.44		
SGOT	Case	126.39	113.94	3.02	<0.0001 S
	Control	85.75	71.44		
SGPT	Case	68.25	79.81	2.83	0.0051 S
	Control	50.84	51.86		
ALP	Case	136.08	76.56	1.28	0.20 NS
	Control	122.86	69.43		
ALB	Case	2.81	0.74	4.50	<0.0001 S
	Control	3.32	0.86		
Bilirubin Conjugated	Case	3.87	5.69	3.74	<0.0001 S
	Control	1.47	2.98		
Bilirubin un-conjugated	Case	1.85	1.63	3.27	<0.0001 S
	Control	1.16	1.30		
Total Bilirubin	Case	5.69	6.39	4.17	<0.0001 S
	Control	2.61	3.72		
Protein	Case	6.49	0.97	0.60	0.55 NS
	Control	6.57	0.95		
Creatinine	Case	1.79	1.82	0.98	0.33 NS
	Control	1.59	0.84		
APRI	Case	5.59	9.23	3.90	<0.0001 S
	Control	1.89	2.14		

Table 4 : base line characteristics like age is significant ($p < 0.01$) among cases, laboratory parameters like platelet count, Aptt, both conjugated and unconjugated bilirubin, albumin are significant in cases($p < 0.01$)

APRI is significant in cases(p value < 0.001) implies that important prognostic tool in cirrhosis patients

Table-5: Comparison of parameters of Survival and Non-survival

Parameters	Group	Mean	s.d.	t-value	p-value
Age	Non-survival	46.22	11.18	0.93	0.38 NS
	Survival	42.52	13.97		
HB	Non-survival	7.18	2.46	3.31	<0.01 S
	Survival	10.11	3.24		
WBC count	Non-survival	9755.56	7659.00	0.02	0.99 NS
	Survival	9797.69	8378.26		
PLC	Non-survival	0.73	0.48	3.22	<0.01 S
	Survival	1.35	1.03		
APTT	Non-survival	41.37	11.63	1.05	0.32 NS
	Survival	37.20	7.60		
PT	Non-survival	23.06	5.31	1.36	0.20 NS
	Survival	20.49	6.29		
INR	Non-survival	1.95	0.50	1.73	0.12 NS
	Survival	1.64	0.53		
SGOT	Non-survival	140.33	148.79	0.30	0.77 NS
	Survival	125.01	110.87		
SGPT	Non-survival	59.44	70.59	0.39	0.71 NS
	Survival	69.12	80.96		
ALP	Non-survival	120.00	35.88	1.21	0.24 NS
	Survival	137.67	79.40		
ALB	Non-survival	2.31	0.31	4.21	<0.001 S
	Survival	2.86	0.76		
Bilirubin Conjugated	Non-survival	6.62	6.38	1.37	0.20 NS
	Survival	3.60	5.58		
Bilirubin un-conjugated	Non-survival	2.98	2.06	1.76	0.11 NS
	Survival	1.73	1.55		
Total Bilirubin	Non-survival	9.60	7.52	1.66	0.13 NS
	Survival	5.30	6.18		
Protien	Non-survival	6.40	1.08	0.27	0.79 NS
	Survival	6.50	0.97		
Creatinine	Non-survival	1.98	0.93	0.57	0.58 NS
	Survival	1.77	1.89		
MELD	Non-survival	26.89	7.04	2.76	0.02 S

	Survival	20.03	7.62		
APRI	Non-survival	6.77	4.77	0.69	0.50 NS
	Survival	5.47	9.57		
Child Pugh Score	Non-survival	10.78	2.33	2.70	0.02 S
	Survival	8.60	2.01		

t-test showed that there was no significant difference in mean APRI of non-survival and survival cases ($t_{198}=0.69;p=0.50$).

However, proportion of patients with APRI>1.5 was significantly higher in non-survival (88.9%) as compared to survival (62.6%) ($Z=4.30;p<0.0001$) shown in table 24

Table-6: Distribution of patients in the two groups

Status	Number	%
Cases	100	50.0%
Control	100	50.0%
Total	200	100.0%

50.0% of the patients were with liver cirrhosis (cases) and rest 50.0% of the patients were without liver cirrhosis (Control). Thus the patients of the two groups were in the ratio 1:1.

Figure : 1 Distribution of patients in the two groups

Table-7: Age and the patients of the two groups

Age (in years)	Cases	Control	TOTAL
17 - 39	41	20	61
Row %	67.2	32.8	100.0
Col %	41.0	20.0	30.5
40 - 60	49	46	95
Row %	51.6	48.4	100.0
Col %	49.0	46.0	47.5
>60	10	34	44
Row %	22.7	77.3	100.0
Col %	10.0	34.0	22.0
TOTAL	100	100	200
Row %	50.0	50.0	100.0
Col %	100.0	100.0	100.0
Mean±s.d.	42.85±13.73	52.89±14.24	

Row% - provides comparison between two groups (Cases and Control) for each age group.

Col% - provides comparison within a group (Cases or Control) for all age groups.

$\chi^2=20.41$; $p<0.0001$ S-Significant

Chi-square (χ^2) test showed that there was significant association between age and the patients of the two groups ($p<0.0001$).

t-test showed that the mean age of cases was significantly lower than Control ($t_{198}=5.08$; $p<0.0001$).

Figure : 2 Age and the patients of the two groups

Table-8: Gender of the patients in both the groups

Gender	Case	Control	TOTAL
Male	85	79	164
Row %	51.8	48.2	100.0
Col %	85.0	79.0	82.0
Female	15	21	36
Row %	41.7	58.3	100.0
Col %	15.0	21.0	18.0
TOTAL	100	100	200
Row %	50.0	50.0	100.0
Col %	100.0	100.0	100.0

Out of 100 patients 85 were male and 15 were female. Chi-squwere (χ^2) test showed that there was no significant association between gender and the patients of the two groups (p=0.26)[$\chi^2=1.21$; p=0.26 NS-Not Significant]. Thus patients of the two groups were more or less equally distributed over gender as shown in table 8.

Figure : 3 Gender of the patients in both the groups

Table-9: Level of Hb and the patients of the two groups

Level of Hb (%)	Cases	Control	TOTAL
<13	83	90	173
Row %	48.0	52.0	100.0
Col %	83.0	90.0	86.5
13 - 17	15	10	25
Row %	60.0	40.0	100.0
Col %	15.0	10.0	12.5
>17	2	0	2
Row %	100.0	0.0	100.0
Col %	2.0	0.0	1.0
TOTAL	100	100	200
Row %	50.0	50.0	100.0
Col %	100.0	100.0	100.0
Mean±s.d.	9.85±3.28	10.03±2.63	

Out of total 173 patients 90 were control and rest 83 both found with <13% Level of Hb as shown in figure : 4

Out of total 25 patients 10 were control and rest 15 both found with 13-17%Level of Hb as shown in figure : 4

Out of total 2 patients 0 were control and rest 2 both found with <17% Level of Hb as shown in figure : 4

$\chi^2=3.28$; $p=0.19$ NS-Not Significant

Chi-squwere (χ^2) test showed that there was no significant association between level of Hb and the patients of the two groups ($p=0.19$). Thus level of Hb was more or less equally distributed among the patients of the two groups.

t-test showed that there was no significant difference in mean level of HB of the patients of the two groups ($t_{198}=0.44$; $p=0.66$).

Figure : 4 Level of Hb and the patients of the two groups

Table 10 : Level of WBC and the patients of the two groups

Level of WBC (per microliter)	Cases	Control	TOTAL
<4000	23	12	35
Row %	65.7	34.3	100.0
Col %	23.0	12.0	17.5
4000-10000	36	54	90
Row %	40.0	60.0	100.0
Col %	36.0	54.0	45.0
>10000	41	34	75
Row %	54.7	45.3	100.0
Col %	41.0	34.0	37.5
TOTAL	100	100	200
Row %	50.0	50.0	100.0
Col %	100.0	100.0	100.0
Mean±s.d.	9793.90±8279.75	9363.90±7140.26	

Out of total 35 patients 12 were control and rest 23 both found with <4000 Level of WBC as shown in figure : 5

Out of total 90 patients 54 were control and rest 36 both found with 4000-10000 Level of WBC

as shown in figure : 5

Out of total 75 patients 34 were control and rest 41 both found with >10000 Level of WBC as shown in figure : 5

$\chi^2=5.71$; $p=0.06$ NS-Not Significant

Chi-square (χ^2) test showed that there was significant no association between level of WBC and the patients of the two groups ($p=0.06$).

t-test showed that there was no significant difference in mean level of WBC of the patients of the two groups ($t_{198}=0.39$; $p=0.70$).

Figure : 5 Level of WBC and the patients of the two groups

Table-11: Level of platelet count and the patients of the two groups

Level of platelet count (mcl)	Cases	Control	TOTAL
<1.3	70	49	119
Row %	58.8	41.2	100.0
Col %	70.0	49.0	59.5
1.3 – 4.5	29	50	79
Row %	36.7	63.3	100.0
Col %	29.0	50.0	39.5
>4.5	1	1	2
Row %	50.0	50.0	100.0
Col %	1.0	1.0	1.0
TOTAL	100	100	200
Row %	50.0	50.0	100.0
Col %	100.0	100.0	100.0
Mean±s.d.	1.29±1.01	1.76±1.01	

Out of total 119 patients 49 were control and rest 70 both found with <1.3 (mcl) Level of Platelet count

as shown in figure : 6

Out of total 79 patients 50 were control and rest 29 both found with 1.3-4.5 (mcl) Level of Platelet count

as shown in figure : 6

Out of total 2 patients 1 were control and rest 1 both found with >4.5 (mcl) Level of Platelet count

as shown in figure : 6

$\chi^2=9.28$; $p=0.009$ NS-Not Significant

Chi-squwere (χ^2) test showed that there was significant no association between level of platelet count and the patients of the two groups ($p=0.06$).

t-test showed that the mean platelet count of cases was significantly lower than Control group ($t_{198}=3.32$; $p<0.0001$).

Figure : 6 Level of platelet count and the patients of the two groups

Table-12: Level of aPTT and the patients of the two groups

Level of aPTT (seconds)	Cases	Control	TOTAL
<29.5	0	15	15
Row %	0.0	100.0	100.0
Col %	0.0	15.0	7.5
29.5 – 35.0	53	54	107
Row %	49.5	50.5	100.0
Col %	53.0	54.0	53.5
>35.0	47	31	78
Row %	60.3	39.7	100.0
Col %	47.0	31.0	39.0
TOTAL	100	100	200
Row %	50.0	50.0	100.0
Col %	100.0	100.0	100.0
Mean±s.d.	37.58±8.05	31.14±13.55	

Out of total 15 patients 15 were control and rest 00 both found with <29.5 seconds Level of aPTT

as shown in figure : 7

Out of total 107 patients 54 were control and rest 53 both found with 29.5-35.0 seconds Level of aPTT

as shown in figure : 7

Out of total 78 patients 31 were control and rest 47 both found with >35.0 seconds Level of aPTT

as shown in figure : 7

$\chi^2 = 18.29$; $p < 0.0001$ S-Significant

Chi-square (χ^2) test showed that there was significant association between level of aPTT and the patients of the two groups ($p < 0.0001$).

t-test showed that the mean aPTT of cases was significantly higher than Control group ($t_{198} = 4.08$; $p < 0.0001$).

Figure : 7 Level of aPTT and the patients of the two groups

Table-13: Level of PT and the patients of the two groups

Level of PT	Cases	Control	TOTAL
11.9 - 13.5	13	18	31
Row %	41.9	58.1	100.0
Col %	13.0	18.0	15.5
>13.5	87	82	169
Row %	51.5	48.5	100.0
Col %	87.0	82.0	84.5
TOTAL	100	100	200
Row %	50.0	50.0	100.0
Col %	100.0	100.0	100.0
Mean±s.d.	20.72±6.22	20.20±6.79	

Out of total 31 patients 18 were control and rest 13 both found with 11.9-13.5 Level of PT as shown in figure : 8

Out of total 169 patients 82 were control and rest 87 both found with >13.5 Level of PT as shown in figure : 8

$\chi^2=0.95$; $p=0.32$ NS-Not Significant

Chi-square (χ^2) test showed that there was no significant association between level of PT and the patients of the two groups ($p=0.32$).

t-test showed that there was no significant in level of PT of the patients of the two groups ($t_{198}=0.056$; $p=0.57$).

Figure : 8 : Level of PT and the patients of the two groups

Table-14: Level of INR and the patients of the two groups

Level of INR	Cases	Control	TOTAL
0.8 - 1.0	5	3	8
Row %	62.5	37.5	100.0
Col %	5.0	3.0	4.0
>1.1	95	97	192
Row %	49.5	50.5	100.0
Col %	95.0	97.0	96.0
TOTAL	100	100	200
Row %	50.0	50.0	100.0
Col %	100.0	100.0	100.0
Mean±s.d.	1.67±0.53	1.57±0.44	

Out of total 8 patients 3 were control and rest 5 both found with 0.8-1.0 Level of INR as shown in figure : 9

Out of total 192 patients 97 were control and rest 95 both found with >1.1 Level of INR as shown in figure : 9

$\chi^2=0.52$; $p=0.47$ NS-Not Significant

Chi-square (χ^2) test showed that there was no significant association between level of INR and the patients of the two groups ($p=0.47$).

t-test showed that there was no significant in level of INR of the patients of the two groups ($t_{198}=1.49$; $p=0.14$).

Figure : 9 Level of INR and the patients of the two groups

Table-15: Level of SGOT and the patients of the two groups

Level of SGOT (units/liter)	Cases	Control	TOTAL
15 - 46	18	34	52
Row %	34.6	65.4	100.0
Col %	18.0	34.0	26.0
>46	82	66	148
Row %	55.4	44.6	100.0
Col %	82.0	66.0	74.0
TOTAL	100	100	200
Row %	50.0	50.0	100.0
Col %	100.0	100.0	100.0
Mean±s.d.	126.39±113.94	85.75±71.44	

Out of total 52 patients 34 were control and rest 18 both found with 15-46 (units/liter)
Level of sGOT

as shown in figure : 10

Out of total 148 patients 66 were control and rest 82 both found with >46 (units/liter)

Level of sGOT

as shown in figure : 10

$\chi^2=6.65$; $p=0.009$ S-Significant

Chi-squwere (χ^2) test showed that there was significant association between level of SGOT and the patients of the two groups ($p=0.009$).

t-test showed that the mean SGOT of cases was significantly higher than Control group ($t_{198}=4.08$; $p<0.0001$).

Figure : 10 Level of SGOT and the patients of the two groups

Table-16: Level of SGPT and the patients of the two groups

Level of SGPT	Cases	Control	TOTAL
7 - 50	59	73	132
Row %	44.7	55.3	100.0
Col %	59.0	73.0	66.0
>50	41	27	68
Row %	60.3	39.7	100.0
Col %	41.0	27.0	34.0
TOTAL	100	100	200
Row %	50.0	50.0	100.0
Col %	100.0	100.0	100.0
Mean±s.d.	68.25±79.81	50.84±51.86	

Out of total 132 patients 73 were control and rest 59 both found with 7-50 Level of SGPT as shown in figure : 11

Out of total 68 patients 27 were control and rest 41 both found with >50 Level of SGPT as shown in figure : 11

$\chi^2=4.36$; $p=0.036$ S-Significant

Chi-square (χ^2) test showed that there was significant association between level of SGPT and the patients of the two groups ($p=0.036$).

t-test showed that the mean SGPT of cases was significantly higher than Control group ($t_{198}=2.83$; $p=0.0051$).

Figure : 11 Level of SGPT and the patients of the two groups

Table-17: Level of ALP and the patients of the two groups

Level of ALP (IU/L)	Cases	Control	TOTAL
38 - 126	60	69	129
Row %	46.5	53.5	100.0
Col %	60.0	69.0	64.5
>126	40	31	71
Row %	56.3	43.7	100.0
Col %	40.0	31.0	35.5
TOTAL	100	100	200
Row %	50.0	50.0	100.0
Col %	100.0	100.0	100.0
Mean±s.d.	136.08±76.56	122.86±69.43	

Out of total 129 patients 69 were control and rest 60 both found with 38-126 (IU/L) Level of ALP

as shown in figure : 12

Out of total 71 patients 31 were control and rest 40 both found with >126 (IU/L) Level of ALP

as shown in figure : 12

$\chi^2=1.76$; $p=0.18$ NS-Not Significant

Chi-square (χ^2) test showed that there was no significant association between level of ALP and the patients of the two groups ($p=0.18$).

t-test showed that there was no significant in level of ALP of the patients of the two groups ($t_{198}=1.28$; $p=0.20$).

Figure : 12 Level of ALP and the patients of the two groups

Table-18: Level of ALB and the patients of the two groups

Level of ALB (g/dL)	Cases	Control	TOTAL
3.5 - 5.0	81	53	134
Row %	60.4	39.6	100.0
Col %	81.0	53.0	67.0
>5.0	19	47	66
Row %	28.8	71.2	100.0
Col %	19.0	47.0	33.0
TOTAL	100	100	200
Row %	50.0	50.0	100.0
Col %	100.0	100.0	100.0
Mean±s.d.	2.81±0.74	3.32±0.86	

Out of total 134 patients 53 were control and rest 81 both found with 3.5-5.0 (g/dL) Level of ALB

as shown in figure : 13

Out of total 66 patients 47 were control and rest 19 both found with 3.5-5.0 (g/dL) Level of ALB

as shown in figure : 13

$\chi^2=17.72$; $p<0.0001$ S-Significant

Chi-square (χ^2) test showed that there was significant association between level of ALB and the patients of the two groups ($p<0.0001$).

t-test showed that the mean ALB of cases was significantly higher than Control group ($t_{198}=4.50$; $p<0.0001$).

Figure : 13 Level of ALB and the patients of the two groups

Table-19: Level of conjugated bilirubin and the patients of the two groups

Level of conjugated bilirubin (mg/dL)	Cases	Control	TOTAL
0.0 - 0.3	81	53	134
Row %	60.4	39.6	100.0
Col %	81.0	53.0	67.0
>0.3	19	47	66
Row %	28.8	71.2	100.0
Col %	19.0	47.0	33.0
TOTAL	100	100	200
Row %	50.0	50.0	100.0
Col %	100.0	100.0	100.0
Mean±s.d.	3.87±5.69	1.47±2.98	

Out of total 134 patients 53 were control and rest 81 both found with 0.0-0.3 (mg/dL)
Level of conjugated bilirubin as shown in figure : 14
Out of total 66 patients 47 were control and rest 19 both found with >0.3 (mg/dL)
Level of conjugated bilirubin as shown in figure : 14

$\chi^2=6.23$; $p=0.021$ S-Significant

Chi-square (χ^2) test showed that there was significant association between level of conjugated bilirubin and the patients of the two groups ($p=0.021$).

t-test showed that the mean conjugated bilirubin of cases was significantly higher than Control group ($t_{198}=3.74$; $p<0.0001$).

Figure : 14 Level of conjugated bilirubin and the patients of the two groups

Table-20: Level of un-conjugated bilirubin and the patients of the two groups

Level of un-conjugated bilirubin	Cases	Control	TOTAL
0.0 - 1.1	22	31	53
Row %	41.5	58.5	100.0
Col %	22.0	31.0	26.5
>1.1	78	69	147
Row %	53.1	46.9	100.0
Col %	78.0	69.0	73.5
TOTAL	100	100	200
Row %	50.0	50.0	100.0
Col %	100.0	100.0	100.0
Mean±s.d.	1.85±1.63	1.16±1.30	

Out of total 53 patients 31 were control and rest 22 both found with 0.0-1.1 (mg/dL)
Level of un-conjugated bilirubin as shown in figure : 15
Out of total 147 patients 69 were control and rest 78 both found with >1.1 (mg/dL)
Level of un-conjugated bilirubin as shown in figure : 15

$\chi^2=5.71$; $p=0.017$ S-Significant

Chi-square (χ^2) test showed that there was significant association between level of un-conjugated bilirubin and the patients of the two groups ($p=0.017$).

t-test showed that the mean un-conjugated bilirubin of cases was significantly higher than Control group ($t_{198}=3.27$; $p<0.0001$).

Figure : 15 Level of un-conjugated bilirubin and the patients of the two groups

Table-21: Level of total bilirubin and the patients of the two groups

Level of total bilirubin	Cases	Control	TOTAL
0.2 - 1.3	31	53	84
Row %	36.9	63.1	100.0
Col %	31.0	53.0	42.0
>1.3	69	47	116
Row %	59.5	40.5	100.0
Col %	69.0	47.0	58.0
TOTAL	100	100	200
Row %	50.0	50.0	100.0
Col %	100.0	100.0	100.0
Mean±s.d.	5.69±6.39	2.61±3.72	

Out of total 84 patients 53 were control and rest 31 both found with 0.2-1.3 Level of total bilirubin as shown in figure : 16

Out of total 116 patients 47 were control and rest 69 both found with >1.3 Level of total bilirubin as shown in figure : 16

$\chi^2 = 5.71$; $p = 0.017$ S-Significant

Chi-square (χ^2) test showed that there was significant association between level of total bilirubin and the patients of the two groups ($p = 0.017$).

t-test showed that the mean total bilirubin of cases was significantly higher than Control group ($t_{198} = 4.17$; $p < 0.0001$).

Figure : 16 Level of total bilirubin and the patients of the two groups

Table-22: Level of protein and the patients of the two groups

Level of protein (g/dL)	Cases	Control	TOTAL
<6.3	42	35	77
Row %	54.5	45.5	100.0
Col %	42.0	35.0	38.5
6.3 - 8.2	54	62	116
Row %	46.6	53.4	100.0
Col %	54.0	62.0	58.0
>8.2	4	3	7
Row %	57.1	42.9	100.0
Col %	4.0	3.0	3.5
TOTAL	100	100	200
Row %	50.0	50.0	100.0
Col %	100.0	100.0	100.0
Mean±s.d.	6.49±0.97	6.57±0.95	

Out of total 77 patients 35 were control and rest 42 both found with <6.3 (g/dL) Level of protein

as shown in figure : 17

Out of total 116 patients 62 were control and rest 54 both found with 6.3-8.2 (g/dL)

Level of protein

as shown in figure : 17

Out of total 7 patients 3 were control and rest 4 both found with >8.2 (g/dL) Level of protein

as shown in figure : 17

$\chi^2=1.33$; $p=0.51$ NS-Not Significant

Chi-square (χ^2) test showed that there was significant no association between level of protein and the patients of the two groups ($p=0.51$).

t-test showed that there was no significant difference in mean level of protein of the patients of the two groups ($t_{198}=0.60$; $p=0.55$).

Figure : 17 Level of protein and the patients of the two groups

Table-23: Level of creatinine and the patients of the two groups

Level of creatinine (mg/dL)	Cases	Control	TOTAL
<0.66	8	11	19
Row %	42.1	57.9	100.0
Col %	8.0	11.0	9.5
0.66 - 1.25	28	32	60
Row %	46.7	53.3	100.0
Col %	28.0	32.0	30.0
>1.25	64	57	121
Row %	52.9	47.1	100.0
Col %	64.0	57.0	60.5
TOTAL	100	100	200
Row %	50.0	50.0	100.0
Col %	100.0	100.0	100.0
Mean±s.d.	1.79±1.82	1.59±0.84	

Out of total 19 patients 11 were control and rest 8 both found with <0.66 (mg/dL) Level of creatinine

as shown in figure : 18

Out of total 60 patients 32 were control and rest 28 both found with 0.66-1.25 (mg/dL) Level of creatinine

as shown in figure : 18

Out of total 121 patients 57 were control and rest 64 both found with >1.25 (mg/dL) Level of creatinine

as shown in figure : 18

$\chi^2=1.14$; $p=0.56$ NS-Not Significant

Chi-square (χ^2) test showed that there was significant no association between level of creatinine and the patients of the two groups ($p=0.56$).

t-test showed that there was no significant difference in mean level of creatinine of the patients of the two groups ($t_{198}=0.98$; $p=0.33$).

Figure : 18 Level of creatinine and the patients of the two groups

Table-24: APRI and the patients of the two groups

APRI	Cases	Control	TOTAL
<0.5	8	25	33
Row %	24.2	75.8	100.0
Col %	8.0	25.0	16.5
0.5 - 1.5	27	39	66
Row %	40.9	59.1	100.0
Col %	27.0	39.0	33.0
>1.5	65	36	101
Row %	64.4	35.6	100.0
Col %	65.0	36.0	50.5
TOTAL	100	100	200
Row %	50.0	50.0	100.0
Col %	100.0	100.0	100.0
Mean±s.d.	5.59±9.23	1.89±2.14	

Out of total 33 patients 25 were control and rest 8 both found with <0.5 Level of APRI as shown in figure : 19

Out of total 66 patients 39 were control and rest 27 both found with 0.5-1.5 Level of APRI as shown in figure : 19

Out of total 101 patients 36 were control and rest 65 both found with >1.5 Level of APRI as shown in figure : 19

$\chi^2=19.26$; $p<0.0001$ S-Significant

Chi-square (χ^2) test showed that there was significant association between APRI and the patients of the two groups ($p<0.0001$).

t-test showed that the mean APRI of cases was significantly higher than Control group ($t_{198}=3.90$; $p<0.0001$).

Figure : 19 APRI and the patients of the two groups

Table-25: MELD Score and the patients of the two groups

MELD Score	Cases	Control	TOTAL
6 - 40	100	100	200
Row %	50.0	50.0	100.0
Col %	100.0	100.0	100.0
TOTAL	100	100	200
Row %	50.0	50.0	100.0
Col %	100.0	100.0	100.0
Mean±s.d.	20.65±7.79	17.66±7.05	

In both the group the MELD Score was within Control limit.

t-test showed that the mean MELD Score of cases was significantly higher than Control group ($t_{198}=2.85;p<0.01$) as shown in fig 20

Figure : 20 MELD Score and the patients of the two groups

Table-26: Other associated factors of the patients

Other associated factors	Number	%	Z-value	p-value
Features of POTS HTN	46	46.0%	1.13	0.25
Ascites	44	44.0%	1.08	0.28
Encephelopathy	28	28.0%	0.89	0.37
Hepato-renal syndrome	18	18.0%	0.51	0.61
Dialysis	1	1.0%	0.17	0.86

Figure : 21 Other associated factors of the patients

Table-27: Child Pug Score of the patients

Child Pug Score	Number	%
5 - Class-A	5	5.00%
6 - Class-A	12	12.00%
7 - Class-B	11	11.00%
8 - Class-B	18	18.00%
9 - Class-B	18	18.00%
10 - Class-C	12	12.00%
11 - Class-C	13	13.00%
12 - Class-C	7	7.00%
13 - Class-C	3	3.00%
14 - Class-C	1	1.00%

Most of the patients were with 8-Class-B (18.0%) and 8-Class-C (18.0%) but these were not significantly higher.

Table-28: Child Pug Score of the patients

Child Pug Score	Number	%
A	17	17.0%
B	47	47.0%
C	36	36.0%
Total	100	100.0%

47.0% and 36.0% of the patients were with Child Pug Score B and C respectively which were significantly higher than Child Pug Score C (17.0%) ($Z=3.04;p<0.002$) as shown in fig 22

Figure : 22 Child Pug Score of the patients

Table-29: Final outcome of the patients

Outcome	Number	%
Died during treatments	9	9.0%
Discharged alive	91	91.0%
Total	100	100.0%

91.0% of the patients were discharged alive which was significantly higher than the patients who died during treatments ($Z=11.59;p<0.0001$) as shown in fig 23.

Figure : 23 Final outcome of the patients

Table-30: Comparison of APRI of Survival and Non-survival

APRI	Non-survival	Survival	TOTAL
<0.5	0	8	8
Row %	0.0	100.0	100.0
Col %	0.0	8.8	8.0
0.5 - 1.5	1	26	27
Row %	3.7	96.3	100.0
Col %	11.1	28.6	27.0
>1.5	8	57	65
Row %	12.3	87.7	100.0
Col %	88.9	62.6	65.0
TOTAL	9	91	100
Row %	9.0	91.0	100.0
Col %	100.0	100.0	100.0
Mean±s.d.	6.77±4.77	5.47±9.57	

$\chi^2 = 2.58$; $p = 0.27$ NS-Not Significant

Chi-square (χ^2) test showed that there was no significant association between APRI and the patients of the two groups ($p = 0.27$).

t-test showed that there was no significant difference in mean APRI of non-survival and survival cases ($t_{198} = 0.69$; $p = 0.50$).

However, proportion of patients with APRI > 1.5 was significantly higher in non-survival (88.9%) as compared to survival (62.6%) ($Z = 4.30$; $p < 0.0001$) as shown in fig 24.

Figure : 24 Comparison of APRI of Survival and Non-survival

Figure : 25 Comparison in mean APRI of Survival and Non-survival

ROC curve & AUC of ROC curve:

The werea under the ROC curve for APRI in detecting cases was 0.693. The optimal cut-off value of APRI in discriminating cases from Control was found to be 3.99 using Youden Method.

Table-31: Efficacy of APRI in detecting liver cirrhosis

Cases	APRI		TOTAL
	+ (>3.99)	- (≤3.99)	
+	33 (16.5%)	67 (33.5%)	100 (50.0%)
-	14 (7.0%)	86 (43.0%)	100 (50.0%)
TOTAL	47 (23.5%)	13 (76.5%)	200 (100.0%)

$\chi^2=10.04$; $p=0.0015$ S-Significant

Chi-square (χ^2) test showed that there was significant association between APRI and Cases ($p=0.0015$).

Table-32: Efficacy of APRI in detecting liver cirrhosis

Comparison	Number	%
TP	33	16.5%
TN	86	43.0%
FN	67	33.5%
FP	14	7.0%
Total	200	100.0%

TP-True Positive, TN-True Negative, FN- False Negative, FP- False Positive

Diagnostic Accuracy = $(TP+TN) / \text{TOTAL CASES} \times 100 = 59.50\%$

Sensitivity = $TP / (TP+FN) \times 100 = 33.00\%$

Specificity = $TN / (TN+FP) \times 100 = 86.00\%$

Positive Predictive Value = $TP / (TP+FP) \times 100 = 70.21\%$

Negative Predictive Value = $TN / (TN+FN) \times 100 = 56.21\%$

DISCUSSION

A prospective follow up study was conducted by us in IPD set up of the Medicine department of Jawaharlal Nehru Medical College, Datta Meghe Institute of Medical Sciences, Wardha to determine the importance of Aspartate aminotransferase-to-platelet ratio index (APRI) as a non-invasive marker for alcohol liver disease among patients with alcoholic liver disease getting treated and admitted in the tertiary care centre for a time period of 1 year. In our study, we estimated the correlation between the APRI score with the severity of cirrhosis with meld and child PUGH score. We also determined the correlation between APRI with various other aetiologies of cirrhosis. In addition to the above, we also tried to correlate APRI with various outcomes of cirrhosis including mortality and morbidity. It is now recently documented through various studies and literature that tried to address the shortcomings in the literature regarding the choice of an ideal non-invasive marker for alcoholic liver disease. Existent research in this field is also mainly focused on western settings, and there is a lack of evidence from India, especially from the central part of India. Moreover, it is documented by several studies that India is marked by the huge burden of alcoholic liver disease leading to complications such as Liver cirrhosis, mainly due to increased alcohol consumption among the Indian population. Thus, considering the need for an investigation to counteract the huge burden, we decided to take our research to determine the importance of Aspartate aminotransferase-to-platelet ratio index (APRI) as a non-invasive marker for alcohol liver disease among patients with alcoholic liver disease getting admitted in Medicine department of Jawaharlal Nehru Medical College, Datta Meghe Institute of Medical Sciences, Wardha

In our study, we took around 200 cases, where 100 acted as cases, and the remaining as controls. The age distribution showed that around 48% of the study participants belonged to the age groups of 40-60 years, and the distribution of Hb showed that around 87% had hb

values less than 13 mg/dl, thus reflecting the higher burden of anaemia among patients with liver failure and chronic liver disease. These findings were observed to be similar to findings put forth by other studies done in various other study settings such as Slaghi et al and Maruyama et al, who estimated the most commonly involved age group is middle age, and anaemia is more prevalent among individuals with alcoholic liver disease (50,51)

With respect to the platelets and the WBC counts, we observed that around 38% had total counts of more than 10000, and with respect to platelets, we observed that almost 3/5th had thrombocytopenia (counts <1.3 lakhs). These findings were also observed to be similar to findings observed by Ogasawara et al, who have also shown that alcoholic liver disease patients tend to have low platelet counts and neutrophilia. (52) These findings suggest rearrangements of platelet profiles due to variations in liver functioning. We also observed that around 40% of the patients had prolonged aPTT values, around 4/5th of the participants showed prolongation of prothrombin time (>13.5 secs), these findings were observed to be similar to findings put forth by a study done by Slaghi et al, who showed that patients experience prolongation of prothrombin time and aPTT values when diagnosed with alcoholic liver disease. (50) Cirrhosis is a condition that causes both coagulopathic and procoagulant conditions. (53) With platelet consumption, there are irregularities in platelet production as well as hypersplenism and reduced synthesis of clotting factors and anticoagulants that are reliant on and independent of Vitamin K. (54) In people with cirrhosis, a lack of vitamin K-dependent clotting factors (II, VII, IX, and X) causes an increased international normalised ratio (INR). Although it is commonly believed that a raised INR indicates that a person is more likely to bleed, this is not the case for cirrhotic individuals, and the INR is less trustworthy than it would be in a person with normal liver function. Similar to this, prothrombin time (PT) has not been shown to be a reliable indicator of GI bleeding in cirrhosis, nor does a prolonged INR indicate a protective function in the

development of hospital-acquired deep vein thrombosis (DVT). (55) There are some but insufficient correlations between INR and superficial bleeding. Additionally, there is scant data to suggest that vitamin K supplementation reduces bleeding or the need for transfusions in cirrhotic patients. (56)

We observed that almost all (96%) cases, had prolonged PT-INR, indicating the derangements in clotting mechanism owing to liver cirrhosis. We also documented that there was a significant difference between the cases and controls with respect to aPTT. These findings were observed to be in line with other findings by Forkin et al and Premkumar et al, who noted that liver cirrhosis can have an adverse effect on the coagulation profile. (57,58)

Taking into reference of the liver function tests and its abnormalities, we observed that around 3/4th of the study participants were found to have increased SGOT, and 1/3rd had an elevated SGPT. We also observed that there was a statistical difference between the distribution of these LFT parameters between the study groups, which was again demonstrated earlier by various other studies done by Sakka et al and Albers et al. (59,60)

With respect to the ALP profile among the cases, around 3/4th had elevated ALP levels, however, we did not observe any significance between the case and the control groups (p value 0.18)

Taking into reference of the conjugated, unconjugated and the total bilirubin into consideration also, we observed that the two study groups (cases vs controls) varied significantly between them (p value <0.05), with the cases group having more bilirubin levels. This finding is also supported by various other studies done by Hopkins et al and Castillo et al who also showed that participants with liver cirrhosis have increased conjugated, unconjugated and the total bilirubin levels. (61,62)

However, comparing the total protein and creatinine levels across the study groups, we did not observe any statistical difference for total protein (6.49 ± 0.97 vs 6.57 ± 0.95 , p value 0.55 in the cases and controls) and for creatinine (1.79 ± 1.82 vs 1.59 ± 0.84 , in the cases and controls, p-value 0.33) Despite having non-significant results, we observed that these findings were observed to be similar and comparable to findings from Heidelbaugh et al, who also showed non significant results between creatine and protein distribution when compared to cases and controls. (63)

With respect to our main outcome of APRI estimation across the study groups, we observed that the mean (sd) distribution of APRI scores between cases and controls was 5.59 ± 9.23 and 1.89 ± 2.14 , which was observed to be statistically significant. (p-value < 0.001) This was observed to be in line with the findings observed by a study done by Castillo et al and Snyder et al, who showed an elevation of APRI among cases with liver cirrhosis. (62, 64)

Considering the associated factors with cirrhosis, we observed that the most commonly seen association was portal hypertension, followed by ascites and encephalopathy. This was also observed to be similar to findings observed by Rabiee et al. (65) It was also noted that around 47% and 36% of the patients were having a Child Pugh Score B and C respectively which were significantly higher than Child Pugh Score C. This finding was observed to be in line with findings from Albers et al. (66) The mortality rates observed were 9% among the cirrhosis cases. A study by Lazo et al, has also shown that the mortality of cases with alcoholic liver disease varies between 3.1 to 16.1%. (67) When we tried comparing the proportion of APRI cases with values > 1.5 across the survivors and non-survivors, we observed that the proportion of patients with $APRI > 1.5$ was significantly higher in non-survival (88.9%) as compared to survival (62.6%) ($Z = 4.30; p < 0.0001$). This was also found to be comparable to the findings observed by Bakula et al. (68)

On comparing the validity of APRI scores in detecting cirrhosis, we observed that the area under the ROC curve for APRI in detecting cirrhosis was 0.693, and the optimal cut-off value of APRI was found to be 3.99 using the Youden Method. Using the same ROC analysis, we tried to obtain the other validation parameters, which showed a sensitivity, specificity, PPV and NPV of 33%, 86%, 70% and 56% respectively. This was also observed to be in line with findings observed by Baranova et al who showed that APRI index had a AUC of 0.82 in detecting cirrhosis. Thus through our study findings, we document that Aspartate Aminotransferase to- Platelet Ratio Index (APRI) could serve as an ideal non-invasive marker for the detection of liver cirrhosis. (69)

CONCLUSION:

To conclude, our study including 200 patients (100 cases and controls) showed that 48% of the study participants belonged to the age groups of 40-60 years, around 87% had anaemia. We documented that there was a significant difference between the cases and controls with respect to aPTT. We also observed that there was a statistical difference between the distribution of these LFT parameters (SGOT, SGPT) between the study groups. We observed a statistically significant difference between the study groups with respect to the distribution of APRI. (p-value <0.001). Considering the associated factors with cirrhosis, we observed that the most commonly seen association was portal hypertension, followed by ascites and encephalopathy. On comparing the validity of APRI scores in detecting cirrhosis, we observed that the area under the ROC curve for APRI in detecting cirrhosis was 0.693, and the optimal cut-off value of APRI was found to be 3.99, with a sensitivity, specificity, PPV and NPV of 33%, 86%, 70% and 56% respectively.

STRENGTHS AND LIMITATIONS

Strengths:

Our study had several strengths:

1. Ours was one of the very few studies that has correlated APRI with the severity of cirrhosis with meld and child PUGH score
2. Our study was one among the few studies that correlate APRI with various aetiologies of cirrhosis
3. Our study was also one among the few studies that tried to compare APRI with various outcomes of cirrhosis in terms of mortality and morbidity from Indian settings, using all validated methods of investigations

Limitations:

Despite all our study had certain limitations:

1. We had a smaller sample size to evaluate the effect outcome on all independent variables
2. Limitations of this study are generally attributed to the observational nature of this study and the constraints of the ability to establish causal relationships between the exposure and outcome
3. The findings are generalisable only to similar study settings, as the study was conducted only from one single centre in south India

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